
Editorial in Medical Research

Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health (AMPPH) Joins Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and Champions Open-Access Science for Global Challenges

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Keywords: Climate change and health; Diamond open access; Open access publishing; Scientific collaboration

Cite this paper as: Chirico F, Rizzo A. *Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health (AMPPH) joins Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and Champions Open-Access Science for Global Challenges.* Adv Med Psychol Public Health. 2026;3(2):131-132. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.16782984

Received: 20 June 2025; Revised: 20 July 2025; Accepted: 27 July 2025; Published Online: 08 August 2025

Dear Readers,

The inclusion of *Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health (AMPPH)* in the *Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)* represents a pivotal achievement. This milestone underscores our commitment to the Open Access Diamond model, ensuring equitable dissemination of knowledge without publication fees, making high-quality, peer-reviewed research accessible to all.

At the heart of AMPPH lies the *International Network for the Advancement of Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health (INAMPPH)*. This global initiative unites scientists, editors, and research groups from diverse disciplines to address pressing global challenges—including climate change, pandemics, and social inequalities.

In a world rife with conflict, INAMPPH stands as a symbol of what scientific collaboration can achieve. While political systems often divide, science offers a model of unity, fostering connections across borders to deliver solutions rooted in evidence, ethics, and compassion.

Addressing global crises through collaboration

AMPPH and INAMPPH embrace an interdisciplinary approach to tackle challenges such as:

- *Climate change*: By integrating research on health impacts, mitigation strategies, and sustainability [1].
- *Global health emergencies*: Drawing on lessons from COVID-19, we prioritize preparedness, equity in resource allocation, and resilience [2].
- *Ethics and spirituality*: Recognizing the role of ethical principles and spiritual dimensions in driving holistic, inclusive solutions [3].

Scientists within INAMPPH act not only as researchers but as thought leaders advocating for peace, cooperation, and sustainable development [4]. This ethos extends to demonstrating the value of ethical research and its potential to inspire policies grounded in shared human dignity.

The importance of open-access science

Our Diamond Open Access model epitomizes transparency and inclusivity. It aligns with our belief that the democratization of scientific knowledge can empower societies worldwide, particularly in under-resourced regions. By eliminating publication fees, we foster global participation, ensuring that groundbreaking research benefits humanity as a whole.

The achievements of AMPPH and INAMPPH are the result of dedicated collaborations across continents. Yet, the challenges we face demand even broader engagement. We invite universities, institutions, and individual researchers to join this endeavor, contributing their expertise to our shared mission.

Together, let us show that science is not just a means of understanding but a tool for uniting the world. Scientists have a responsibility—and the ability—to demonstrate how interdisciplinary cooperation can inspire transformative solutions.

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